

An Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Current Oil Spill Response Strategies in the Niger Delta Region, Nigeria

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Article History:

Received: 12.07.2025 Revised: 01.09.2025 Accepted: 13.09.2025 Published: 16.09.2025

Abstract

The study assessed the effectiveness of current oil spill response strategies in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. Four hundred copies of the questionnaire were administered to the residents of the six communities randomly selected in the study area. It adopted descriptive statistics using frequency and percentage as well as inferential statistics in the form of Chi-square for the data analysis. Findings revealed that the majority (51.6%) of respondents were males and more than 50% were between the age of 20 and 50 years. The majority of the respondents (55.7%) had tertiary education. Furthermore, findings revealed that more than 60% of total respondents agreed that the use of bio-remediated materials, onsite bioremediation, ex-situ bioremediation and boomers were the effective current oil spill response strategies in the Niger Delta region, Nigeria. There was a significant variation in the effectiveness of current oil spill response strategies such as bioremediation materials ($\chi^2=129.71$, $p=0.000$), use of onsite bioremediation ($\chi^2=128.52$), the use of ex-situ bioremediation ($\chi^2=194.56$; $p=0.000$) and the use of boomers ($\chi^2=167.64$; $p=0.000$). The study concluded that there are existing response strategies in the study location but they are not effective due to poor multi-agency collaboration, misinterpretation and inefficiency of information communication, poor coordination among stakeholders, long delays in information and response teams, and poor communication among stakeholders which are as well varied significantly among the communities. It is therefore recommended among others that the collaboration of the multi-agency should be reinstated and adequately established.

Keywords: *Response strategies, Oil Spill, Ex situ, On-Site, Bioremediation, Collaboration.*

Suggested citation: Franklin, M., Obafemi, A.A., Amama, S.A., & Iwuoha, S.E. (2025). An Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Current Oil Spill Response Strategies in the Niger Delta Region, Nigeria. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(5), 107-120. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(5\).12](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(5).12)

Introduction

There has been an increasing global usage of petroleum and its associated products, which has

equally led to increasing exposure to threats associated with the process of its exploration, production and consumption. The movement of this product from the production stages to the

consumer involves different processes and modes of transportation including tankers, pipelines, rail vehicles, and tank trucks. There is however the reality that, with the ways these products are processed, moved and stored at transfer points, terminals, flow stations, refineries, and even to the point of dispelling at the filling stations to the final consumers, accidents could occur at any point. This implies that, as Oil transportation continues to increase globally to meet people's needs, communities in this operating environment could be at risk of the oil spill impacts especially the risk posed to human and aquatic lives (Jernelöv, 2010; Barron et al. 2020; Bebetidoh et al. 2020; & Lusweti, et al, 2022), hence the imperatives for sound response strategies.

According to Lusweti, et al (2022), though the oil industry is a source of revenue and foreign exchange for an economy, nevertheless, oil exploration is an inherent risk to the environment and has become of great concern to both human and aquatic life, due to the pollution of water resources, especially surface water resources (Ite, et al. 2013), often resulting in toxicity accretion and ecological contamination. In the words of Bayode & Adewunmi (2011), all through the numerous stages of oil exploration, fluids are discharged into the environment, most especially from the discharge activities such as drill cuttings, drilling mud, and produced fluids such as oil and water along with other chemicals injected to enhance the separation of oil from water (Bayode & Adewunmi 2011; Ite, et al. 2013). This exploration process is associated with possible environmental impacts as a result of inappropriate transportation, disposal and treatment of oil exploration and mining waste, land degradation, water and air pollution to adverse effects on the community's sources of livelihood. (Lusweti, et al 2022).

Nigeria is one of the largest producers of crude oil in Africa, the eleventh largest producer of petroleum, the eighth largest exporter of crude oil and has the tenth largest proven reserve of crude oil in the world (Akuru & Okoro, 2011 & Ezenwa, et al 2022). Similarly, the Niger Delta region has also been adjudged as one of the most ecologically sensitive regions in Nigeria since the

inception of oil and gas exploration and exploitation from the region, with oil spills regular occurrence resulting in environmental degradation and causing a significant tension between the host communities and the multinational oil companies operating in the region. Therefore, the high level of oil exploration activities going on in the region has subjected most of the oil-producing communities to various negative environmental impacts associated with leakages and accidental spills that occur regularly during the exploration, refining, transportation and storage of this product (Ezenwa, et al 2022; Oyodele, et al. 2016). Also, the various degrees of environmental degradation and pollution, destroy the traditional livelihood support system, kill plants and animals in the estuarine zone, endanger fish hatcheries, as well as disrupt and decrease major food chains and yields. All of these have caused mutagenic and carcinogenic effects thereby subjecting the environment and human health to significant risks. (Romanus, et al. 2015).

Ultimately, effective Oil spill response and strategy requires that when a huge oil spill occurs for instance, a fast, prompt and compelling reaction is crucial with a specific end goal to limit the monetary effect and the harm to both nature and human life is inevitable (Ishak, et al, 2020 & Al-Majed, et al. 2015). Thus, to remedy crude oil-polluted sites, a variety of soil remediation techniques exist including but not limited to only physical and chemical remediation techniques. However, these technologies are expensive and can lead to the incomplete decomposition of contaminants (Ding, et al. 2020; Yu, et al., 2020; Liu, et al 2021). But the emergence of Bio-remediation, being one of the latest scientific strategies that have been discovered to be cost-effective, possesses great potential in removing crude oil from the soil and degrading petroleum hydrocarbons without leaving behind any toxic products in the soil ecosystem (Ezenwa, et al 2022 & Oyodele, et al. 2016).

Lin, et al (2010), developed an innovative bioprocess technology, Systematic Environmental Molecular Biotechnology (SEMBT), to treat petroleum oil-contaminated soil in the field, by combining bioaugmentation

and biostimulation using the landfarming procedure with the operational strategy of reseeded previous biopile soils in series. Molecular microarray biotechnology was used for monitoring during the bioremediation process. This integrated operational strategy of SEMBT was found to improve the biodegradation of hydrocarbon as well as bioremediation efficiency (Lin, et al 2010). With these techniques, scholars agree that most of the physical and chemical properties of the soil such as aeration, pH, water-holding capacity, and ion exchange capacity can be improved through the process (Ezenwa, et al 2022; Nkereuwem, et al. 2010; Lim, et al. 2016; Atlas, et al. 2015; Okeke, et al 2022; Liu, et al 2021).

However, the steps taken to mitigate and respond to the devastation associated with spills in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria, such as through environmental regulations for the oil industry, provision of security surveillance and partnering with community leaders for early warning notification on illegal oil bunker and pipeline vandalism are strategies that seem to fail to yield effective results. Disaster risks do not only exist because of the presence of a physical hazard, rather they are compounded by the presence of vulnerability (Abdeen, et al 2021). Hence, there is an urgent need for a change of focus and strategy of disaster management from hazard to vulnerability reduction; from reactive to proactive; from single agency to partnerships; and from response management to risk management aimed to ultimately achieve resilience. This requires a well-coordinated multi-agency collaboration to play a key role, even though the process of collaboration often face some challenges due to various reasons. It is in recognition of these challenges, that the Sendai Framework Priority Action 2 on “strengthening disaster risk governance”, calls for national and sub-national governments to strengthen their collaboration among relevant stakeholders to manage risks in a proactive manner (Abdeen, et al 2021).

A couple of studies have been carried out on oil spills and oil exploration activities in the Niger Delta region in Nigeria and their associated impacts on the community's social and economic activities, sustainable environmental

management, and so on (Opiyo et al. 2015; Mutua 2016; Mugendi, 2020; Ikenna, et al 2023). There is however a lack of insufficient systematic analyses of the environmental or health impacts of oil exploration, drilling and extraction activities and the enabling mitigation strategies (Lave & Lutz 2014). Therefore, the present study assessed the effectiveness of current oil spill response strategies in the Niger Delta Region, identifying some gaps that could be filled by strengthening disaster risk governance through an effective and efficient multi-agency collaboration. (UNDRR, 2015). This paper thus harps on the need for strategy and process that creates up-to-date and tailored oil spill contingency plan (OSCP) (Short,2023), as a key step to ensure that the operating environment and protocols by oil exploration companies do not continue to subject the communities at risk of an oil spill to the potential impact of an incident on people, the environment, their assets and livelihoods.

Materials and Methods

Research Location

The study was carried out in the Delta, Bayelsa and Rivers States located in the Niger Delta Region (Figure 1). The Niger Delta region is located in southern Nigeria, encompassing a vast expanse of land between approximately 4°N to 6°N latitude and 5°E to 7°E longitude. This region covers an area of approximately 70,000 square kilometers (27,000 square miles), making it one of the world's largest and most ecologically diverse deltas. Situated at a relatively low elevation, the Niger Delta region is characterized by its proximity to sea level, with an average height ranging from just a few meters above sea level to slightly higher areas. The delta is a sprawling network of rivers, tributaries, and wetlands, crisscrossed by the Niger and Benue rivers, and eventually emptying into the Gulf of Guinea.

This vast delta, crisscrossed by numerous rivers and waterways, supports a mosaic of ecosystems. Mangrove swamps dominate the coastal areas, with various species of mangroves like *Rhizophora* and *Avicennia*, thriving in the

brackish waters. Moving inland, the vegetation transitions into freshwater swamp forests with towering *Raphia* palms, oil palms, and various fruit trees. The study area enjoys a tropical monsoon climate which is distinguished by distinct wet and dry seasons. The weather in this region is greatly influenced by its proximity to the Atlantic Ocean. During the wet season, which typically spans from April to October, the

area experiences heavy rainfall, with the peak occurring from June to September. This abundant precipitation is due to the southwest monsoon winds bringing moisture-laden air from the Atlantic, resulting in lush, green landscapes and flooding of low-lying areas. Temperatures during this period range from 24°C to 31°C, creating a humid and often uncomfortable environment.

Figure 1. Niger Delta Region showing the Selected LGAs in Delta, Bayelsa and Rivers States

Nigeria's Niger Delta, a region in the south of the nation, is a hive of varied social activities and is important to the country's economy. Because it has a sizable share of Nigeria's oil reserves, the region contributes economically to the country's oil and gas industry. The revenue generated from oil production significantly impacts Nigeria's GDP, making the Niger Delta central to the country's economic prosperity. However, despite its economic significance, the region faces challenges, such as environmental degradation, social unrest and inadequate infrastructure, resulting from decades of oil exploration and exploitation. These issues have spurred social activities, including activism and advocacy for environmental protection and resource ownership rights.

Methodology

A survey research design was used for this study. A purposive sampling technique was used to select the six oil spill communities in the Niger Delta region. The purposive sampling technique is appropriate to this study in the sense that the researcher use purposive sampling to select the six oil spill communities in the Niger Delta region in order to save cost, energy and time due to security challenges facing the terrain which enables the researcher to easily access and collect the needed data in the communities. The study sampled 400 respondents using the Taro Yamane formula of sample size which spread across the 6 communities selected for this study. The communities are Benikurkuru, Odimodi, Basambiri, Ogbolomabiri, Ojobo and Bomu. In each of the six communities, a convenient sampling technique was used to collect data.

Convenience sampling as the name implies is a specific type of non-probability sampling method in which data are collected within the scope of the study or sampled population who are conveniently available to participate in the study. Therefore, convenience sampling is appropriate to this study in the sense that it helped to collect data from any person within the field that gave consent to be part of the respondents for the study. The instrument for this study was a self-developed Questionnaire named Oil Spill Response Strategy and Disaster Need Assessment in Niger Delta. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency count, simple percentages and tables to illustrate the demographic characteristics of respondents and answer the research questions. The 400 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents while 384 copies were retrieved and used for further analysis. Inferential statistics of chi-square was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significant levels while a score of $p < 0.05$ was rejected and a score of $p > 0.05$ was accepted.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Distribution of Respondents

Table 1 contains the demographic characteristics of the respondents. There were 51.6% male respondents, while 48.1% were female respondents. The analysis also showed that 18.3% of the respondents were from the ages

between 11 and 20 years, 26.6% of the respondents were from the ages between 21 and 30 years, 20.1% were between 31 and 40 years, 20.8% were between 41 and 50 years, while 14.1% were between the ages of 51 and 60 years. Furthermore, the educational level of the respondents showed that 12.2% were primary certificate holders, 32.1% of the respondents were secondary school certificate holders and the majority of the respondents which is 55.7% were graduates from higher institutions. The occupation of the respondents revealed that 9.4% of the respondents were fishermen, 17.7% of the respondents were farmers, 20.8% were businessmen/women, 29.9% were civil servants, while 21.1% were students. The analysis also shows the marital status of the respondents whereby 13.3% of the respondents were singles, 34.4% of the respondents were married, 25.0% of the respondents were divorced, while 7.3% of the respondents were widows/widowers. Similarly, the community-based participation in the study by the respondents indicated that 26.0% of the respondents were from the Gbaramatu community, 11.7% were from Odimodi community, 26.0% were from Bassambiri community, 15.1% of the respondents were from Ogbolomabiri community, 10.7% of the respondents were from Ojobo community and 10.4% of the respondents were from Bomu community.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents (n=384)

S/NO	Demographic Characteristics	Response	Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	(a) Males	198	51.6
		(b) Females	186	48.4
		Total	384	100
2	Age	(a) 11 – 20	71	18.5
		(b) 21 – 30	102	26.6
		(c) 31 – 40	77	21.1
		(d) 41 – 50	80	20.8
		(e) 51 – 60	54	14.1
		Total	384	100
3	Educational Level	(a) Primary	47	12.2
		(b) Secondary	123	32.1
		(c) Tertiary	214	55.7
		Total	184	100
4	Occupation	(a) Fishing	36	9.4

		(b) Farming	68	17.7
		(c) Business	80	20.8
		(d) Civil servant	115	29.9
		(e) Student	85	21.1
		Total	384	100
5	Marital Status	(a) Single	128	13.3
		(b) Married	132	34.4
		(c) Divorce	96	25.0
		(d) Widow/widower	28	7.3
		Total	384	100
6.	Names of Community	Gbaramatu	100	26.0
		Odimodi	45	11.7
		Bassambiri	100	26.0
		Ogbolomabiri	58	15.1
		Ojobo	41	10.7
		Bomu	40	10.4
		Total	384	100

Effectiveness of Current Oil Spill Response Strategies

Table 2 shows the result of the effectiveness of current oil spill response strategies in the Niger Delta region. It is revealed that the majority of the respondents which is 50.0% strongly agreed with the statement that the use of bio-remediated is one of the effectiveness of current oil spill response strategies in the Niger Delta region, 27.1% agreed, while 17.2% disagreed and 5.7% strongly disagreed. Item 8 shows that 36.6% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that the use of onsite bioremediation is one of the effectiveness of current oil spill response strategies in the Niger Delta region, the majority of the respondents which is 38.8% agreed, 16.9% disagreed and only 10.7% strongly disagreed. Item 9 shows that the majority of the respondents which is 40.4% strongly agreed, 37.0% agreed, 16.1% disagreed and only 6.5% strongly disagreed that the use of ex situ bioremediation is one of the effectiveness of current oil spill response strategies in the

Niger Delta region. The result of the study in item 10 shows that 34.1% strongly agreed, 40.9% agreed, 16.9% disagreed and only 8.1% strongly disagreed that the use of boomers is one of the effectiveness of current oil spill response strategies in the Niger Delta region. Finally, the result of the study in item 11 shows that 28.1% of the respondents strongly agreed, 38.0% agreed that the use of skimmers is one of the effectiveness of current oil spill response strategies in the Niger Delta region while 18.9% disagreed and 15.1% strongly disagreed.

The variation in the effectiveness of current oil spill response strategies among the communities in the Niger Delta region in Table 3 (Appendix) shows that the use of bio-remediated, the use of onsite bioremediation, the use of ex-situ bioremediation and the use of boomers were significant and as such the null hypothesis was rejected in each case while the alternative hypothesis was accepted and retained at $p < 0.05$.

Table 2. The Effectiveness of Current Oil Spill Response Strategies in the Niger Delta Region (n=384)

Response Strategies	Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
The use of bio-remediated	(a) SA	104	27.1
	(b) A	192	50.0
	(c) D	66	17.2
	(d) SD	22	5.7
	Total	384	100
The use of onsite bioremediation	(a) SA	129	36.6
	(b) A	149	38.8

	(c) D	65	16.9
	(d) SD	41	10.7
	Total	384	100
The use of ex situ bioremediation	(a) SA	155	40.4
	(b) A	142	37.0
	(c) D	62	16.1
	(d) SD	25	6.5
	Total	384	100
The use of boomers	(a) SA	131	34.1
	(b) A	157	40.9
	(c) D	65	16.9
	(d) SD	31	8.1
	Total	384	100
The use of skimmers	(a) SA	108	28.1
	(b) A	146	38.0
	(c) D	72	18.8
	(d) SD	58	15.1
	Total	384	100

Gaps and Weaknesses of Response Strategies

Table 4 shows the responses on the gaps and weaknesses in the response strategy in the Niger Delta region. Item 12 shows that 34.4% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that poor multi-agency collaboration is one of the gaps and weaknesses in the response strategy in the Niger Delta region, 22.9% disagreed, while 8.3% strongly disagreed. Item 13 shows that 28.4% of the respondents strongly agreed that misinterpretation and inefficiencies of information communication are one of the gaps and weaknesses in the response strategy in the Niger Delta region, 32.8% agreed, 26.6% disagreed and only 12.2% strongly disagreed. Item 14 shows that 32.0% of the respondents strongly agreed that poor coordination among stakeholders is one of the gaps and weaknesses in the response strategy in the Niger Delta region, 40.1% agreed, while 21.9% disagreed and only 6.0% strongly disagreed. The respondents in item 15 shows that 31.3% strongly agreed,

45.8% agreed, 12.5% disagreed and 10.4% of the respondents strongly disagreed that long delays in information and response team are one of the gaps and weaknesses in the response strategy in the Niger Delta region.

Finally, the result in item 16 shows that the majority of the respondents which is 44.8% strongly agreed with the statement that poor communication among stakeholders is one of the gaps and weaknesses in the response strategy in the Niger Delta region, 34.4% agreed, 12.5% disagreed and only 8.3% strongly disagreed. The analysis on chi-square analysis of the gaps and weaknesses in the response strategy in the Niger Delta region as displayed in Table 5 (Appendix) reveals that poor multi-agency collaboration, misinterpretation and inefficiency of information communication, poor coordination among stakeholders, long delays in information and response team, and poor communication among stakeholders varied significantly among the communities at $p < 0.05$.

Table 4. Gaps and Weaknesses in the Response Strategy in the Niger Delta Region

Item	Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Poor multi-agency collaboration	(a) SA	132	34.4
	(b) A	132	34.4
	(c) D	88	22.9
	(d) SD	32	8.3
	Total	384	100

Misinterpretation and inefficiencies of information communication	(a) SA	109	28.4
	(b) A	126	32.8
	(c) D	102	26.6
	(d) SD	47	12.2
	Total	384	100
Poor coordination among stakeholders	(a) SA	123	32.0
	(b) A	154	40.1
	(c) D	84	21.9
	(d) SD	23	6.0
	Total	384	100
Long delays in information and response team	(a) SA	120	31.3
	(b) A	176	45.8
	(c) D	48	12.5
	(d) SD	40	10.4
	Total	384	100
Poor communication among stakeholders	(a) SA	172	44.8
	(b) A	132	34.4
	(c) D	48	12.5
	(d) SD	32	8.3
	Total	384	100

Evaluation of Oil Spills Response Strategy and Post-Disaster Needs Assessment

This study evaluated the oil spill response strategy and post-disaster needs assessment in the Niger Delta region. The result of the study showed that Majority of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that the use of bio-remediated is one of the effectiveness of current oil spill response strategies in the Niger Delta Region. This is similar to the study by (Atlas, et al. 2015; Okeke, et al 2022; Ayilara & Babalola 2023) that reported that Bioremediation or biodegradation is a process that has to do with how micro-organisms digest crude oil molecules through enzymatic processes, resulting in carbon dioxide, biomass, and water-soluble chemicals. Some bacterial types prevalent in the climate such as mold, yeast, archaea and fungus may feed on crude oil molecules (Mekkiyah, et al 2023).

The result of the study also reveals that the use of onsite bioremediation is one of the effectiveness of the current oil spill response strategy. This is in line with the research by (Mustafa, et al. 2023; Li, et al 2020; Xu, et al 2022) who reported that Onsite bioremediation involves scraping polluted subsoil through biological methods, such as hydrocarbon breakdown by physical procedures, chemical processes or microorganisms such as soil venting or air sparging, are used for removing

toxins from subsoil and groundwater. The hydrocarbon degradation method may need vertical and horizontal drilling and it works better on sandy soils than clay soils. Surface pollution may be treated using spreading devices thus it also increases aerobic bacteria growth by providing them with oxygen.

The findings of this study revealed that the use of ex situ bioremediation is one of the effectiveness of the current oil spill response strategy. This result is consistent with the findings of Xu, et al (2022) on in-situ remediation and Lin, et al (2010) on innovative and integrated bioprocess technology, Systematic Environmental Molecular Biotechnology (SEMBT), for field applications in treating petroleum oil-contaminated soil. It equally aligns with the study by Mekkiyah, et al (2023), who reported that Ex situ bioremediation approaches need off-site soil treatment by incinerating, chemically extracting, or washing the soil to remove hydrocarbons. Steam stripping, combustion, extraction and biological treatments are major ex situ treatment procedures. Chemical extraction uses solvents to dissolve or suspend soil pollutants (Lin, et al 2010 & Mekkiyah, et al 2023).

Also, from the result of the study, it was found that the majority of the respondents agree that poor multi-agency collaboration is one of the gaps and weaknesses in the response strategy.

This is consistent with the study by Salmon, et al. 2010; Jiang & Yuan, 2019; Li, et al, 2020; Liu, et al, 2021; Short,2023) who conducted a study on the gaps and weaknesses in the response strategy. The outcome calls for enhanced collaboration among relevant stakeholders, improved funding and motivation, as well as better coordination among the multi-agencies involved (Abdeen, et al 2021).

Conclusion

The study concluded that there are existing response strategies in the study location but they are not effective due to poor multi-agency collaboration, misinterpretation and inefficiency of information communication, poor coordination among stakeholders, long delays in information and response teams, and poor communication among stakeholders which are as well varied significantly among the communities. It is therefore recommended among others that the collaboration of the multi-agency should be reinstated and adequately established. The government should organize an awareness campaign that will improve the knowledge and attitude of the community on the oil spill response strategy and post-disaster needs assessment in the Niger Delta region. The government should organize seminars and workshops on the challenges of effective oil spill response strategy and post-disaster needs assessment in the Niger Delta region.

Acknowledgement

The authors appreciate the platform and support provided by the Centre for Disaster Risk Management and Development Studies, University of Port Harcourt for this research.

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Appendix

Table 3. Summary of Chi-Square Analysis on the Effectiveness of Current Oil Spill Response Strategies in the Niger Delta Region

Item	Community	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Df	χ^2	P-value	Decision
The use of bio-remediated	Benikurkuru	21(27.1)	61(50.0)	18(17.2)	0(5.7)	100	15	129.713	0.000	Ho Rejected
	Odimodi	21(12.2)	10(22.5)	14(7.7)	0(2.6)	45				
	Bassambiri	12(27.1)	43(50.0)	34(17.2)	11(5.7)	100				
	Ogbolomabiri	9(15.7)	38(29.0)	0(10.0)	11(3.3)	58				
	Ojobo	21(11.1)	20(20.5)	0(7.0)	0(2.3)	41				
	Bomu	20(10.8)	20(20.0)	0(6.9)	0(2.3)	40				
	Total	104(104.0)	192(192.0)	66(66.0)	22(22.0)	384				
The use of onsite bioremediation	Benikurkuru	26(33.6)	43(38.8)	21(1.9)	10(10.7)	100	15	128.517	0.000	Ho Rejected
	Odimodi	21(15.1)	20(17.5)	0(7.6)	4(4.8)	45				
	Bassambiri	45(33.6)	45(38.8)	5(16.9)	5(10.7)	100				
	Ogbolomabiri	20(19.5)	18(22.5)	2(9.8)	18(2)	58				
	Ojobo	17(13.8)	3(15.9)	20(6.9)	1(4.4)	41				
	Bomu	0(13.8)	20(15.5)	17(6.8)	3(4.3)	40				
	Total	129(129.0)	149(149.0)	65(65.0)	41(41.0)	384				
The use of ex situ bioremediation	Benikurkuru	27(40.4)	31(37.0)	27(16.1)	15(6.5)	100	15	194.555	0.000	Ho Rejected
	Odimodi	1(18.2)	33(16.6)	10(7.3)	1(2.9)	45				
	Bassambiri	27(40.4)	61(37.0)	11(16.1)	1(6.5)	100				
	Ogbolomabiri	27(23.4)	17(21.4)	14(9.4)	0(3.8)	58				
	Ojobo	40(16.5)	0(15.2)	0(6.6)	1(2.7)	41				
	Bomu	33(16.1)	0(14.8)	0(6.5)	7(2.6)	40				
	Total	155(155.0)	142(142.0)	62(62.0)	25(25.0)	384				
The use of boomers	Benikurkuru	21(34.1)	53(40.9)	25(16.9)	1(8.1)	100	15	174.244	0.000	Ho Rejected
	Odimodi	20(15.4)	25(18.4)	0(7.6)	0(3.6)	45				
	Bassambiri	29(34.1)	41(40.9)	15(16.9)	15(8.1)	100				
	Ogbolomabiri	20(19.8)	38(23.7)	0(9.8)	0(4.7)	58				
	Ojobo	21(14.0)	0(16.8)	5(6.9)	15(3.3)	41				
	Bomu	20(13.6)	0(16.4)	20(6.8)	0(3.2)	40				
	Total	131(131.0)	157(157.0)	65(65.0)	31(31.0)	384				
The use of skimmers	Benikurkuru	31(28.1)	48(38.0)	1(18.8)	20(15.1)	100				
	Odimodi	21(12.7)	0(17.1)	15(8.4)	9(6.8)	45				

	Bassambiri	45(28.1)	35(38.0)	20(18.8)	0(15.1)	100	15	167.643	0.000	Ho Rejected
	Ogbolomabiri	11(16.3)	23(22.1)	15(10.9)	9(8.8)	58				
	Ojobo	0(11.5)	20(15.6)	1(7.7)	20(6.2)	41				
	Bomu	0(11.3)	20(15.2)	20(7.5)	0(6.0)	40				
	Total	108(108.0)	146(146.0)	72(72.0)	58(58.0)	384				

Key: Figures in brackets are the expected frequencies

Table 5. Chi-Square Analysis of the Gaps and Weaknesses in the Response Strategy in the Niger Delta Region

Item	Community	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Df	χ^2	P-value	Decision
Poor multi-agency collaboration.	Benikurkuru	41(34.4)	37(34.4)	14(22.9)	8(8.3)	100	15	116.278	0.000	Ho Rejected
	Odimodi	13(15.5)	31(15.5)	1(10.3)	0(3.8)	45				
	Bassambiri	21(34.4)	30(34.4)	41(22.9)	8(8.3)	100				
	Ogbolomabiri	9(19.9)	17(19.9)	24(13.3)	8(4.8)	58				
	Ojobo	24(14.1)	1(14.1)	8(9.4)	8(3.4)	41				
	Bomu	24(13.8)	16(13.8)	0(9.2)	0(3.3)	40				
	Total	132(132.0)	132(132.0)	88(88.0)	32(32.0)	384				
Misinterpretation and inefficiency of information communication.	Benikurkuru	26(28.4)	31(32.8)	28(26.6)	15(12.2)	100	15	102.602	0.000	Ho Rejected
	Odimodi	13(12.8)	31(14.8)	1(12.0)	0(5.5)	45				
	Bassambiri	21(28.4)	30(32.8)	37(26.6)	12(12.2)	100				
	Ogbolomabiri	7(16.5)	17(19.0)	24(15.4)	10(7.1)	58				
	Ojobo	18(11.6)	1(13.5)	12(10.9)	10(5.0)	41				
	Bomu	24(11.4)	16(13.1)	0(10.6)	0(4.9)	40				
	Total	109(109.0)	126(126.0)	102(102.0)	47(47.0)	384				
Poor coordination among stakeholders.	Benikurkuru	33(32.0)	45(40.1)	14(21.9)	8(6.0)	100	15	94.759	0.000	Ho Rejected
	Odimodi	13(14.4)	31(18.0)	1(9.8)	0(2.7)	45				
	Bassambiri	21(32.0)	34(40.1)	37(21.9)	8(6.0)	100				
	Ogbolomabiri	9(18.6)	23(23.3)	24(12.7)	2(3.5)	58				
	Ojobo	23(13.1)	5(16.4)	8(9.0)	5(2.5)	41				
	Bomu	24(12.8)	16(16.0)	0(8.8)	0(2.4)	40				
	Total	123(123.0)	154(154.0)	84(84.0)	23(23.0)	384				
Long delays in information and response team.	Benikurkuru	38(31.3)	44(45.8)	8(12.5)	10(10.4)	100	15	104.862	0.000	Ho Rejected
	Odimodi	10(14.1)	35(20.6)	0(5.6)	0(4.7)	45				
	Bassambiri	18(31.3)	45(45.8)	27(12.5)	10(10.4)	100				
	Ogbolomabiri	9(18.1)	32(26.6)	7(7.3)	10(6.0)	58				
	Ojobo	24(12.8)	1(18.8)	6(5.1)	10(4.3)	41				

	Bomu	21(12.5)	19(18.3)	0(5.0)	0(4.2)	40				
	Total	120(120.0)	176(176.0)	48(48.0)	40(40.0)	384				
Poor communication among stakeholders.	Benikurkuru	43(44.8)	25(34.4)	16(12.5)	16(8.3)	100	15	140.104	0.000	Ho Rejected
	Odimodi	42(20.2)	3(15.5)	0(5.6)	0(3.8)	45				
	Bassambiri	42(44.8)	50(34.4)	8(12.5)	0(8.3)	100				
	Ogbolomabiri	11(26.0)	38(19.9)	1(7.3)	8(4.8)	58				
	Ojobo	10(18.4)	16(14.1)	11(5.1)	4(3.4)	41				
	Bomu	24(17.9)	0(13.8)	12(5.0)	4(3.3)	40				
	Total	172(172.0)	132(132.0)	48(48.0)	32(32.0)	384				

Key: Figures in brackets are the expected frequencies

